

Prior Predictive Check: BMA Weights

Observed Data (black) vs. Prior Simulations (blue)

— y — y_{rep}

Prior Predictive Check: BMA Intercept

Observed Data (black) vs. Prior Simulations (blue)

— y — y_{rep}

Prior Predictive Check: BMA Scale

Observed Data (black) vs. Prior Simulations (blue)

Prior Predictive Check: BMA Full

Observed Data (black) vs. Prior Simulations (blue)

— y — y_{rep}

Prior Predictive Check: BMA State-Dependent Intercept

Observed Data (black) vs. Prior Simulations (blue)

Prior Predictive Check: BMA State-Dependent Inter+Weights

Observed Data (black) vs. Prior Simulations (blue)

Prior Predictive Check: Hierarchical Intercept

Observed Data (black) vs. Prior Simulations (blue)

— y — y_{rep}

Prior Predictive Check: Hierarchical Scale

Observed Data (black) vs. Prior Simulations (blue)

— y — y_{rep}

Prior Predictive Check: Hierarchical Full

Observed Data (black) vs. Prior Simulations (blue)

